

CSES meeting "Supporting Election Studies in the Balkans"

Country-specific overviews of electoral research

Slovenia

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CURRENT CHARACTERISTICS OF ELECTORAL STUDIES&DATA

- 2 prevailing segments of longitudinal research of the elections exist in Slovenia, which have so far never been unified in one big national election research project:
 - 1) General social survey (SJM) from 1968 on that measure party support, ideology, values in regard to party/electoral choice;
 - 2) from 1990s analysis of elections: a) in 1990s as a part of the wider sociological analysis; b) from 2000 on political sciences focused analysis of all various types of elections from the perspectives of party system, rules, candidate selection, campaign, participation, geography, socio-economic factors, social psychology, PR..)
- Thus, so far election data can be 'extracted' from various **micro, macro** and **contextual** types of data mainly for the **purposes of monitoring, evaluating or analysing elections and election phenomena**

CURRENT STRUCTURE OF ELECTORAL STUDIES&DATA

TYPES OF DATA <http://www.cessda.org/accessing/themes/elections.html>; [CESSDA - Council of European Social Science Data Archives www.cessda.org](http://www.cessda.org/)

- Macro data (electoral results): Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia , National Electoral Commission, European election database;
- Micro data: national general social surveys; international surveys; 'pulls' politbarometers; elite populations studies, commercial pools;
- Contextual types of data: electoral programs, interviews; other campaign material, like posters, leaflets.., coalition agreements

DATA SUPPORT

- Financial and institutional support for macro data is provided by the state apparatus and state budget directly
- Financial and institutional support for micro and contextual data is provided mostly through public research funds for which various research institutions can apply in the frameworks of:
 - Research Programms
 - Basic research studies
 - Target research projects
 - Applied research projects
 - Bilateral research projects
 - EU projects

MACRO DATA

- Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia – Elections, available at: http://www.stat.si/eng/tema_splosno_volitve.asp
- National Electoral Commission – Voting procedures and documentation (e.g. voting legislation, timetables, ballots, candidate lists, results) Available at: <http://www.dvk.gov.si/>. For 2011 early national parliamentary elections: <http://volitve.gov.si/dz2011/en/index.html>,
- European election database: http://www.nsd.uib.no/european_election_database/.

CONTEXTUAL DATA

- Other types of data, like: election documents: manifestos, leaflets, posters, other campaign materials, media reports, TV confrontations, interviews...
- Mostly post-election analysis (from 1990 on) by the Institute of Social Sciences of the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana: <http://www.fdv.uni-lj.si/English/Research/>, mainly Centre for Political Sciences Research of the Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Ljubljana (CPSR): http://www.politoloske-raziskave.si/index.php?m_id=home&lang=2
- Mostly gathered as a result of the project works:
 - Programme
 - Basic research studies (in average between 3-5 years)
 - Target research projects (in average between 1-2 years)
 - Applied research projects (in average between 1-2 years)
 - Bilateral research projects (in average 2)
 - EU projects (so far in the frameworks of the COST action)
 - Other networks: like MARPOR, Euromanifestos, Freedom House, election briefings for European Journal of Political Research, EPERN, etc.

CONTEXTUAL DATA: RESEARCH PROJECTS (IN)DIRECTLY RELATED TO THE ANALYSIS OF THE ELECTIONS (as referred by the official data of SICRIS: www.sicris.izum.si)

- Programme ‚Political Research‘ 2,4 FTE (1.1.1999-31.12.2003; 1.1.2004-31.12.2008; 1.1.2009-31.12.2014; head [Fink Hafner, Danica](#)) – analysis of the elections as one of many other relevant political sciences research topics

Basic research project: Political science, interests, democracy (Politična znanost, interesi, demokracija; [Fink Hafner, Danica](#); 1.1.1996-30.6.2001)

Basic research project: [Processes and problems of the consolidation of democracy \(Procesi in problemi konsolidacije demokracije; Fink Hafner, Danica; 1.7.1998-30.6.2001\)](#)

Basic research project: The determinants of (dis)trust in the National Assembly of the RS (Dejavniki v oblikovanju (ne)zaupanja v Državni zbor; [Fink Hafner, Danica](#); 1.9.2000-31.12.2002)

- [Post-doctoral research project: The relationships between European party federations and Slovenian political parties \(Odnosi med evropskimi strankarskimi federacijami in slovenskimi političnimi strankami; Fink Hafner, Danica, Krašovec, Alenka\); 1.7.2002-30.6.2004\)](#)

- [Target research project: The analysis of the development of Slovenian parliamentarism from the first beginnings to the establishment of the National Assembly of the RS \(Analiza razvoja slovenskega parlamentarizma od prvih začetkov do ustanovitve Državnega zbora Republike Slovenije \(Zajc, Drago, 1.1.2004-30.1.2005\)](#)

- Basic research project: Pre-election campaign and democratic evolution of state and society” (Kustec Lipicer, Simona; 1. 5. 2009 – 30. 4. 2012)

- EU COST Action IS0806 “The True European Voter: A Strategy for Analysing the Prospects of European Electoral Democracy That Includes the West, the South and the East of the Continent,” (2009-2014)

MICRO DATA

National and International social surveys being implemented by the **Public Opinion and Mass Communication Research Center** at the Faculty of Social Sciences in Ljubljana (http://www.cjm.si/cjm_english) :

- the Slovene Public Opinion Survey (SJM) regularly from 1968 on
 - **omnibus survey program includes a wide variety of topics** with extensive demographic data including past, current election support, where electoral data present approx. 1/3 of the whole survey questioners
 - only some of the electoral data are continuous series
- Original national data versions of international comparative survey series (mostly as part of [SJM](#)) - E.g. 1) European Social Survey (ESS); 2) ISSP; 3) Comparative Study of Electoral Systems (CSES); 4) Consolidation of Democracy in Central and Eastern Europe; 5) Projekt European/World Values Survey; 6) Value Systems of the Citizens and Socio-Economic Conditions (<http://www.cjm.si/?q=SJM>, <http://adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/serija/CSES/>)
- Politbarometer (1995-2005): monthly, quarterly telephone survey

MICRO DATA

Financial support through national project applications:

- Programme: [Slovenian Public Opinion Survey](#) (1.1.1999-31.12.2013; head: Niko Toš)
- Various other basic, target, applied research projects, where part of the public opinion questions have always been related to the election data (for the whole list see <http://www.cjm.si/projekti> and <http://sicris.izum.si/search/rsr.aspx?opt=3&lang=eng&id=4528>)

Centre has a national network of over 200 experienced interviewers and set up a survey laboratory with CATI facilities

Original data are available by the **Social Science Data Archives**

In the last few years a range of new, mostly commercial and media driven pre- election social surveys have been conducted by private research agencies/institutes.

Social Science Data Archives (ADP)

<http://www.adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/>

- Micro data from all kind of studies at one place free of charge; registration required;
- Original national data versions of international comparative survey series (mostly as part of [SJM](#))
 - E.g. [CSES](http://adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/serija/CSES/): <http://adp.fdv.uni-lj.si/opisi/serija/CSES/> ; Others include [ESS](#), [EVS](#), [WVS](#), [ISSP](#), [NDB](#), [TD](#)
- EU integration studies series (national specific, international):
 - [EU](#) , [EU Index](#) , [EES](#), [CEEB](#), [CCEB](#), [EB](#)
- 'pulls' politbarometer:
 - [PB](#); [Slovenian Pulse](#)
- Miscellaneous
 - [KORUP](#), [ODZIV](#)(some pre-referendums data), [PODDZ](#)
- *National contextual electoral data (protection of copyright and neighbouring rights; issue sensitivity; anonimity)

Data that are yet not available in ADP

- Exit pools, web survey panel, daily cati omnibus: See [Batagelj 2010](#)

 Trends are becoming very important and in three countries in the region SLO, CRO and SRB they converge to tight results

Parliamentary elections Croatia 2007

% HDZ vs SDP; source: VALICON Daily CATI Omnibus, weekly moving averages

http://www.valicon.net/hr/valicon/aktualnosti/novosti/40/sdp_okrenuo_trend_8211_o_pobjedniku_odlucuje_odaziv_biraca_i_dijaspora.html

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Publications out of micro data - Some illustrations:

- **J.Š.: Explaining the Effect of Electoral Losers' Status on Democratic Legitimacy Beliefs: Slovenia 1996 - 2010. November 2010;**
 - **Based on PB survey from 1996 onward**
 - **Descriptive aggregate monthly/quarterly results and micro data analysis combined**
- **Cumulative micro-data of monthly and quarterly surveys, Completion rate \approx 40%, Weighting for demographic structure**
 - **Total N > 100.000**

J.Š. Democracy support and its meanings: equality and freedom (draft, 2012)

Chart: Support for democracy (% positive) by liberal and social meaning (based on SJM2011 – WVS and some national specific variables)

PUBLICATIONS out of contextual, micro & macro electoral data

Some illustrations of the basic ones:

- Ex-, mid-term, post-electoral scientific-based research reports, books, articles, analysis & research data, as well as also daily commentaries, ,columnists' style
- TOŠ, Niko et al (ed). Values in transformation I-IV , SJM documents 1968-2009 (*Vrednote v prehodu I-IV. SJM dokumenti I-IV; 1968-2009*) . Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede
- TOŠ, Niko et al (ed). Politbarometer 1995-. Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede
- FINK-HAFNER, Danica (ed). Elections 1990 (*Volitve '90 : prispevki za politološko analizo : zbornik referatov*). Ljubljana: Slovensko politološko društvo, 1990, pp. 64-82.
- FINK-HAFNER, Danica , STRMČNIK, Berni (ed.). Making of Slovenian statehood (*Nastajanje slovenske državnosti: zbornik referatov*). Ljubljana: Slovensko politološko društvo, 1992
- TOŠ, Niko. Voters and political parties (Volilci in politične stranke). *Teor. praksa*, 1992, 29 (1/2): 109-122.
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- BERNIK, I. (1994). Politics and Society in Post-Socialism. V: Haller, M. and Richter, R. (eds.): Toward a European Nation?, M.E. Sharpe, Armonk, 126-138.
- BERNIK, I., MALNAR, B., Toš, N. (1996). Die Paradoxa der instrumentellen Akzeptanz von Demokratie. *Oestereichische Zeitschrift fuer Politikwissenschaft*, 25, 3, 339-356.
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- KROPIVNIK, Samo. *Slovenian voters in geographical, social and ideological space: analysis of 1990 and 1992 elections*. Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, 1998.
- BERNIK, Ivan, KURDIJA, Slavko, MALNAR, Brina, UHAN, Samo. Values and elections (Vrednote in volitve.) IN: TOŠ, Niko (ed). *Pogledi na reforme : družboslovne refleksije na predlog reform : Slovenija 2005-2006*, Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, 2006, pp. 29-40.

PUBLICATIONS out of contextual, micro & macro electoral data

Some illustrations of the basic ones:

FINK-HAFNER, Danica. Slovenia. *European Journal of Political Research*, 2004 on

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FINK-HAFNER, Danica, BOH, Tomaž (ed.). *Parliamentary elections 2000 (Parlamentarne volitve 2000)* Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, 2002.

FINK-HAFNER, Danica, ANTIĆ, Milica G. The 2002 presidential elections in Slovenia. *Electoral studies*, 2004

FINK-HAFNER, Danica, BOH, Tomaž (ed.). *Presidential elections 2002 (Predsedniške volitve 2002)*, Ljubljana: Fakulteta za družbene vede, 2003.

BREZOVŠEK, Marjan, HAČEK, Miro. Political participation on the local level : the role of the city districts in Slovenia. *Cent. Eur. polit. sci. rev.* 2004, 5(15): 74-94

KUSTEC LIPICER, Simona, KROPIVNIK, Samo, MAKSUTI, Alem. 2006 Local elections campaign analysis (Analiza zmagovitih kampanj v mestnih občinah na lokalnih volitvah leta 2006). *Lex localis*, 2008, 6 (3): 333-372

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ŠTEBE, Janez. *Explaining the effect of electoral losers' status on democratic legitimacy beliefs : Slovenia 1996-2010*. Budapest: Hungarian Academy of Sciences and Obuda Cultural Centre: 2010

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- For more check [Personal Bibliographies](#) on COBISS.Si

CHALLENGES AND PROBLEMS

In general various types of electoral data and analysis in Slovenia have been conducted and analysed systematically and continuously from the late 1960s, and analytically as well from independence on, BUT NO INSTITUTIONAL SUPPORT FOR CENTRAL NATIONAL ELECTION STUDY has been established so far, which causes set of problems/obstacles:

- Constant uncertainty whether we would be able to gather and conduct future national election relevant data and studies, because no fixed grants for these purposes are guaranteed
- Constant problems with the types and quality of data and analysis due to the lack of a stable longitudinal support for the implementation of the national election studies
- Bounded possibility to build the nation's own unified scientific based election study tradition, but still:
 - Systematic pre-post election national specific survey
 - Exhaustive data sources collection available